

Gardner defines intelligences as, 'the ability to solve problems or to create products that are valued within one or more cultural settings.' He believes that human cognitive competencies are better described in terms of asse of abilities, talents or mental skill which he calls intelligences. According to Gardner everyone possesses seven distinct intelligences, i.e. verbal, logical, musical, intrapersonal, interpersonal, and bodily. Recently Gardner added two more one of them is naturalistic and other one is existential intelligence. Multiple intelligence allows students to realize their strengths & weakness, it gives the opportunity to understand the dynamics of the core elements for the education so to develop the strong man power & develop the research fields this study gives directions to use various specific skills, values for becoming a part of knowledge society.

Objectives:-

1. To find out the Multiple Intelligences factors among students.
2. To find out the dominant factor of Multiple Intelligences by using MI inventory.
3. To compare Multiple Intelligences between girl's and boy's students of S.R.T.M.U.Nanded.

Hypothesis:-

- There will be no significant difference between Multiple Intelligence of M. Ed. & M.P.Ed. Campus Students of Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathawada University Nanded.
- There will be no significant difference between Multiple Intelligence of M. Ed. Girl's and boy's students.
- There will be no significant difference between Multiple Intelligence of M.P. Ed. Girl's and boy's students.
- There will be no significant difference between Multiple Intelligence of M. Ed. Boy's and M.P.Ed. boy's students.
- There will be no significant difference between Multiple Intelligence of M. Ed. Girl's and M.P.Ed. girl's students.

Scope of Research:-

- The scope of research is related to S.R.T.M.U. Nanded campus only.

- The present research is related to the academic year 2011-2012.
- The scope of research study is related to the Multiple Intelligences of M.Ed. and M.P.Ed. Campus students of S.R.T.M.U. Nanded.
- The scope of research is related to the study of Multiple Intelligence factors only.

Limitations of Research:-

- Related research work is limited for S.R.T.M.U. Nanded campus only.
- Related research work finds Multiple Intelligences of M.Ed. and M.P.Ed. Campus students of S.R.T.M.U. Nanded.
- Related research is limited for academic year 2011-2012.

Methodology:-

For this presented research study researcher has been selected survey research method. The survey method gather data from a respectively large number of cases at a particular time, it is not concerned with characteristics of individual as individual it is concerned with the generalized statistic that result, when data are abstract from a number of individual cases. It is essentially cross-sectional.

Population:-

For this present research researcher has selected M.Ed. and M.P.Ed. campus Students of swami Ramanand Teerth Marathawada university Nanded studying at the year 2011-12.

M.Ed. students	M.P.Ed. students
40	40

Sample:-

From the entire population researcher has been selected sample by using purposive sampling method to collect the data and sample consisting 15 girls & 15 boy's of M.Ed. And 15 girls & 15 boy's of M.P.Ed. campus students.

M.Ed.

M.P.Ed.

<u>Girls</u>	<u>Boys</u>	<u>Girls</u>	<u>Boys</u>
<u>15</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>15</u>	<u>15</u>

Tool:-

There are various research tools like questionnaire, verbal interviews, observation, rating scale, inventories are used mostly to collect the data in survey method depending upon the type of survey. To find out students Multiple Intelligence, researcher used multiple intelligence inventory made by Walter Mckenize for data collection. Following things were done by researcher to use this inventory.

- Communication with Guide and Lecturers
- Interpretation of ideas
- Pre-research
- Search
- Evolution

In this inventory there was Ninety statements related of Nine types of Multiple Intelligence distributed in Nine sections, each section of intelligence have Ten statements. These statements were based on following nine types of Multiple Intelligence-

1. Naturalistic Intelligence.
2. Musical Intelligence.
3. Logical Intelligence.
4. Existential Intelligence.
5. Kinesthetic Intelligence.
6. Verbal Intelligence.
7. Visual Intelligence.

Statistical Parameter:-

Percentage, Mean, Standard deviation, graph and t-test are used for analyze and interpretation of the collected data.

Data Analysis & Interpretation:-

Table No.1

<i>Sr. no.</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Calculated t- value</i>	<i>Table t- value at the significant level 0.005</i>
<i>1</i>	<i>Boy's</i>	<i>56.44</i>	<i>1.12</i>	<i>98</i>	<i>-12.44</i>	<i>1.98</i>
<i>2</i>	<i>Girls</i>	<i>59.55</i>	<i>1.39</i>			

Table No.2

<i>Sr.no.</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Calculated t- value</i>	<i>Table t- value at the significant level 0.005</i>
<i>1</i>	<i>M.Ed boys (15)</i>	<i>55.44</i>	<i>1.89</i>	<i>48</i>	<i>3.22</i>	<i>2.01</i>
<i>2</i>	<i>M.Ed girls(15)</i>	<i>57.44</i>	<i>2.51</i>			

Major Findings:-

- Every student possesses multiple intelligence factors.
- The total percentage of each intelligence shows variety among nine types. Therefore it indicates that multiple intelligence in varying amount.
- The dominant factors of multiple intelligence among the M.Ed. and M.P.Ed. boys students are existential, logical, kinesthetic, naturalistic intelligence.

- The dominant factors of multiple intelligence among the M.Ed. and M.P.Ed. girls students are logical, existential, intrapersonal and verbal intelligence.
- There is significant difference between multiple intelligence of boys and girls campus students of M.ed. and M.P.Ed. students.
- There exist significant difference multiple intelligence of M.Ed. boys and girls students of SRTMUN.
- There exist significant difference multiple intelligence of M.Ed. boys M.P.Ed. boys students of SRTMUN.
- There exist significant difference multiple intelligence of M.Ed. girls M.P.Ed girls students of SRTMUN.

Recommendations:-

- Teacher, parents and students should know about the multiple intelligences theory.

	Intelligence	Skills and career preference
1	Verbal-linguistic intelligence Well developed verbal skills and sensitivity to the sounds, meanings and rhythms of words	Skills- listening, speaking, writing, teaching Careers- poet, journalist, writer, teacher, lawyer, politician
2	Mathematical- logical intelligence Ability to think conceptually and abstractly, and capacity to discern logical or numerical pattern	Skills- problem solving (logical & math), performing experiments. Careers- scientists, engineers, accountants, mathematician
3	Musical intelligence Ability to produce &	Skills- singing, playing instruments, composing

	appreciate rhythm, pitch & timber	music Careers- Musician, disc jockey, singer, composer
4	Visual-spatial intelligence Capacity to think in images and pictures, to visualize accurately & abstractly	Skills- puzzle building, painting, constructing, fixing, designing objects Careers- sculptor, artist, inventor, engineer
5	Bodily-kinesthetic intelligence Ability to control one's body movements & to handle object skillfully	Skills- dancing, sports, hands on experiments, acting Careers- athlete, dancer, actor, firefighter
6	Interpersonal intelligence Capacity to detect and respond appropriately to the moods, motivations and desires of others	Skills- seeing from other perspectives, empathy, counseling, co-operating Careers- counselor, salesperson, politician
7	Intrapersonal intelligence Capacity to self aware & in tune with inner feelings, values, beliefs and thinking processes	Skills- Recognize one's S/W, reflective, aware of inner feelings Careers- Researchers, philosophers, theorists
8	Naturalist intelligence Ability to recognize & categorize plants, animals	Skills- Recognize one's connection to nature, apply science theory to

	and other objects in nature	life <i>Careers-</i> scientist, naturalist ,landscape architect
9	<i>Existential intelligence</i> Sensitivity and capacity to tackle deep questions about human existence	<i>Skills-</i> Reflective and deep thinking, design abstract theories <i>Careers-</i> scientist, philosophers.

- Dominant factor of multiple intelligence helps to indicate students learning style.
- Multiple intelligence theory is useful to design different teaching strategies for teachers.
- Outcomes of determining students MI studies may be also useful aspect of curriculum and instruction.
- The Multiple intelligences can be enhanced with the use of technology.

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